

SURVEY AND ANALYSIS OF NGOS AND GOVERNMENT SCHEMES FOR ENVIRONMENT: A CASE STUDY OF JALGAON DISTRICT.

S.P.Baviskar*,J.K.Thakur¹, P.R.Patil².

*School of Earth Sciences, Solapur University, Solapur, ¹

Centre for Environment Education Pune, ²

School of environmental & Earth Sciences, NMU, Jalgaon.

INTRODUCTION

The definition we wish to use is that nongovernmental organization (NGO) should aim to be non-profit, non-commercial and non-government. It should subscribe to universal humanitarian values and practices. It should have capacity, and be ready to be held accountable for its actions.¹ A NGO is a legally constituted organization created by natural or legal persons that operates independently from any government and a term usually used by governments to refer to entities that have no government status. In the cases in which NGOs are funded totally or partially by governments, the NGO maintains its non-governmental status by excluding government representatives from membership in the organization. The term is usually applied only to organizations that pursue some wider social aim that has political aspects, but that are not overtly political organizations such as political parties. Unlike the term "intergovernmental organization", the term "non-governmental organization" has no generally agreed legal definition. In many jurisdictions, these types of organization are called "civil society organizations" or referred to by other names

Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and Voluntary action have been part of the historical legacy. In early 20th century, several voluntary efforts were started in the fields of education, health etc. The NGOs became prominent after independence, especially after 1970s. Development practitioners, government officials and foreign donors consider that Non-Governmental organizations by the virtue of being small-scale, flexible, innovative and participatory are more successful in reaching the poor and in poverty alleviating. This consideration has resulted in the rapid growth of NGOs involved in initiating and implementing rural development programmes. According to the estimates of the working

groups of NGOs, there are about 30,000 NGOs in India. A rapid growth took place in the 1980s and the early 1990s. The concept of NGOs and Social welfare are not new. After independence too, there was a lot of talk about the role of NGOs and people's participation when we started our planning process in the early 50s. The British Government in India spent minimum resources on social welfare programmes and so voluntary agencies played an important role in developing programmes for the poor, the destitute, women and children.²

International non-governmental organizations have a history dating back to at least 1839. It has been estimated that by 1914 there were 1083 NGOs. International NGOs were important and the movement for women's suffrage, and reached a peak at the time of the World Disarmament Conference. However, the phrase "non-governmental organization" only came into popular use with the establishment of the United Nations Organization in 1945. The definition of "international NGO" (INGO) is first given in on February 27, 1950: it is defined as "any international organization that is not founded by an international treaty". The vital role of NGOs and other "major groups" in sustainable development was leading to intense arrangements for a consultative relationship between the United Nations and non-governmental organizations.

Rapid development of the non-governmental sector occurred in western countries as a result of the processes of restructuring of the welfare state. Further globalization of that process occurred after the fall of the communist system and was an important part of the Washington consensus.

Globalization during the 20th century gave rise to the importance of NGOs. Many problems could not be solved within a nation. International treaties and international organizations such as the World Trade Organization were perceived as being too centred on the interests of capitalist enterprises. Some argued that in an attempt to counterbalance this trend, NGOs have developed to emphasize humanitarian issues, developmental aid and sustainable development. A prominent example of this is the World Social Forum, which is a rival convention to the World Economic Forum held annually in January in Davos, Switzerland. The fifth World Social Forum in Porto Alegre, Brazil, in January 2005 was attended by representatives from more than 1,000 NGOs. Some have argued that in forums like these, NGOs take the place of what should belong to popular movements of the poor. Others argue that NGOs are often imperialist in nature, that they sometimes operate in a radicalized manner in third world countries, and that they fulfil a similar function to that of

the clergy during the high colonial era. The philosopher Peter Hall ward argues that they are an aristocratic form of politics. Whatever the case, NGO transnational networking is now extensive.³

NGO type can be understood by orientation and level of co-operation. NGO type by orientation Charitable orientation, Service orientation, Participatory orientation, Empowering orientation. NGO type by level of co-operation Community- Based Organization, City Wide Organization, National NGOs, International NGOs.

Activities Undertaken by NGO's in protecting environment and health⁴ Solid waste management This includes both municipal solid waste and bio-medical wastes. Civic Exnoras play a major role in assisting the Municipal Corporation in the collection of garbage from individual households and the deposition of the same in secondary collection points by appointing street beautifiers in the concerned areas. With its experience over the years, Exnoras has realised that this was merely a relocation of waste rather than management of solid waste. NGO's have now started focusing its efforts on the concept of Zero Waste Management, by which practically all wastes can be converted into wealth through recycling. Exnora is also addressing the problem of handling and disposal of bio- medical wastes, and is trying to find a solution beneficial to all concerned. Citizens' Waterways Monitoring Programme (WAMP), this programme was started with the sole purpose of developing clean and pollution free waterways in cities and for creating a healthy living environment for all city dwellers. WAMP was formed in 1991, as a joint programme with several NGOs and individuals dedicated to the cause of developing clean waterways in the city. Community Sanitation Improvement Projects, Inadequate sanitation facilities are a major problem to human health, especially so in the neglected low- income areas and slum settlements. NGO's concept of self- help is best displayed by the community sanitation improvement projects in these areas. Two of the most successful projects have been at the at Narikkurava (Gypsy) Colony in Indira Nagar, Chennai and at Giriappa Road in T. Nagar, Chennai. Student Environment Programme (STEP), this program has a dual role - of creating environmental awareness amongst the student community and to develop each child's mind resources through various personality development programs. A teachers' manual and an activity book that have been brought out as a part of this program are designed in the 'do-and learn' format and provide an easy understanding of the problems faced by us and at the same time kindles the mind to find remedial measures.

The Civic Exnoras in the city have been instrumental in planting trees for the purpose of beautification of roads, parks, playgrounds, burial grounds, etc., with the larger perspective of environmental protection. NGO's have propagated the system of rain harvesting in several residential areas in the city with the aim of exploiting one or another important water source, viz., and rainwater. Many cities suffer from perennial water problems every summer and therefore it is important that all avenues of water source be tapped. By using simple and inexpensive techniques the NGO (Exnora) has arrived at a method to conserve a large part of the 110 cm of rain that we receive annually. A Water Conservation Committee constituted in Chennai by Metro Water Supply and Sewerage Board Exnora is a core member. The task of pollution control in India is complex due to the large number of heavy, large and small-scale industries involved. Further, the rise in the number of vehicles coupled with poverty and the large population puts tremendous pollution pressure on air, water and land.

NGO's Role in Pollution Control, The success of India's environmental programmes depends greatly on the awareness and consciousness of the people. A National Environmental Awareness Campaign has been launched to sensitize people to the environmental problems through audio -visual programmes, seminars, symposia, training programmes etc. Paryavaran Vahinis have been constituted in 184 Districts involving the local people to play an active role in preventing poaching, deforestation and environmental pollution. 4000 NGOs have been given financial assistance for creating environmental awareness. An Environmental Information System (ENVIS) network has been setup to disseminate information on environmental issues. India has a large network of NGO's, which are involved in spreading the message of sustainable development to the public.

STUDY AREA

The NGOs visited by us in Jalgaon city and Taluka's in Jalgaon city

There are following NGOs in Jalgaon city

1. Shri.Ashtavinayak Shaikhanik and Sanskrutik Mandal

Reg.no- maha.5766/Jalgaon-30/8/2000

2. School of Environment

Reg.no-maha-7103/Jalgaon

3. Khandesh Nature Conservation Society

Mahabal Colony, Jalgaon

4. Orachid Nature Foundation

Reg.no-f-11321-2002

5. Vanyajeev Savarkshan bahu-uddeshiy sanstha

Reg.no- maha-10699 Jalgaon

NGOs in talukas of Jalgaon Districts

1. Bhusawal- Upaj Urja Paryavaran Jal

Reg.no- maha-7180/Jalgaon

2. Bhusawal-Green Earth Foundation

Reg.no- maha-11015/Jalgaon 30-8-09

3. Yawal-Go Vigyan Anusandhan va Bahuddeshiya Santha

Haripura village, Tq. Yawal, Dist. Jalgaon.

Reg.no- maha-6955 Jalgaon-14-1-03

f-6276-Jalgaon-23-12-04

4. Pachora-Girna –Tapi Janvikas Paryavaran Sanstha

Reg.no- maha-10341/Jalgaon-2008

f-9262/Jalgaon

5. Chalisgaon-Jivraksha Charitable Trust

Reg.no- maha- e-1062 Jalgaon-2000

Chalsgaon-Nehru Yuva Mandal

6. Patonda village, Tq. Pachora, Dist. Jalgaon

Reg.no- maha-6256 Jalgaon-2004

7. Chopada - Dhiarye Multipurpose Association

Reg.no- maha-10336

8. Amlner-Udan Pakshi Mitra Sanstha

Reg.no- maha-11364-Jalgaon

9. Amlner-Garud Zep Pakshi va Nisarg Seva Pratishtan

Reg.no- maha-8399-Jalgaon

METHODOLOGY

The present investigation has adopted exploratory nature. The nature of data obtained for the present study is qualitative in nature. The data/information was collected from 14 NGOs in Jalgaon District of North Maharashtra.

1. For NGOs survey we collected the information about addresses and contact numbers of the NGOs in Jalgaon District.
2. visited their NGOs officers, area where they are working and resource person of NGO

3. The questionnaire set by us gets filled by them.
4. Collected the Information about methodology of work, type of work
5. Information about training activity, job opportunities.
6. Visited the area/region where they are working.
7. Collected the information regarding their future plans.
8. Predicted the environmental problems facing by NGOs and control on it.

Questionnaire for Govt. Schemes

1. Schemes name, Sponsored by, Start year Implementation/description.
2. Area/Region, Purpose, Benefits, Eligibility criteria, Fund.
3. Concern people, Current status, Problem arises, Specific output.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

We carried out survey from Jalgaon District during the period of January 2011 to April 2011. There are 14 NGOs in Jalgaon District (5 in Jalgaon city and 9 in talukas of Jalgaon District), as all them are registered. Every NGO has different type of work and methodology. All the NGOs are of different characteristic as per their area of work like awareness project, tree plantation, programme conduct in school / colleges, environment day celebration awards, conferences, forest conservation, wild life conservation. It was observed that two NGOs from Jalgaon city and all the nine NGOs / taluka's have no funding from other government or any trustee. The NGOs are using self money, as they are working for environment showing their affection towards environment.

The analysis of questionnaire from all 14 NGO's from Jalgaon city, Taluka's in Jalgaon District and Government schemes are tabulated in Table 1, 2 and 3 respectively. The NGOs in Jalgaon city, Taluka's in Jalgaon District and Government schemes by Maharashtra state as summarised as following,

NGOs in Jalgaon city:

After thoroughly discussion with the peoples associated with the NGOs in Jalgaon city and interpretation of data, it was observed that, all the five NGOs are working in the field of environmental awareness and conservation programme. These NGOs have been established during 2000-2010. These NGOs are working in different thrust areas related to environment awareness, protection and conservation.

1. Shri.Ashtavinayak Shaikhanik and Sanskrutik Mandal:

The organization Shri.Ashtavinayak Shaikhanik and Sanskrutik Mandal established in 2000 have funding from government of about 15-20 lakh per year for implementation of Environment awareness programmes. Its main focus of work is on Jal Swarajya project and water irrigation project. The project has been carried out in nineteen villages in six talukas of Jalgaon District and 47 villages from Nandurbar District. The organization has carried out tree plantation programme in nineteen villages without getting any funding.

2. School of Environment:

The organization conducts various programmes regarding environment education and conservation. They conduct environmental tours for school students, public awareness, awareness against use of plastic bags etc. They have contribution in Satpuda bachav andolan.

3 Khandesh Nature Conservation Society:

The organization works on conservation of natural resources, tree and wild life protection. It is also working in Satpuda bachav andolan to protect nature.

4. Orchid nature foundation:

After establishment in the year 2002, the organization is working on environmental education, conservation and protection. The organization does awareness among people against tree cutting in festivals such as Holi, awareness against use of plaster of Paris. It was also aware the public to celebrate the festivals such as diwali without using crackers.

Major projects undertaken by the organization includes Bird census, Cleaning of Mehrun lake in Jalgaon city The lake cleaning work was considered by United Nations Organization (UNO).

The organization awarded as Srushti award in 2009 for contribution in environment conservation.

5. Vanyajeev Saurakshan Bhahu-uddeshiya sanstha:

The organization works in the field of Snake protection and conservation. The awareness among public is done with the help of snake presentation programme and information is given to the public.

NGOs in Taluka's of Jalgaon District:

We have carried out survey from Nine NGOs in different talukas of Jalgaon District. These organizations were working in different areas of environment protection and

conservation. All the organizations don't have funding from government or Trustee. These organizations are conducting environment awareness programmes in Schools and colleges.

1. Upaj (Urja Paryavaran Jal):

The organization was established in 2003 in Bhusawal town. It mainly works in the field of energy, environment, and water conservation. The organization works in coordination with Maha Urja through Zilha Parishad for solar energy programme, P.C.R.A. (Petroleum Conservation Research Association), M.E.D.A. (Maharashtra Energy Development Agency), M.N.R.E. (Ministry of New and Renewable energy).

2. Green Earth foundation (Bhusawal):

The organization mainly works on Tree plantation. Programmes regarding environmental awareness are conducted in Schools and Colleges.

3. Go vityan anusandhan Bhahu-uddeshiya santha (Haripura Tal. Yawal):

The organization has 100 cows of its own and four gobar gas tanks of 6 m³. The electricity (about 15 hp) produced from gobar gas plant is provided to the tribal students of the school. Production of crops using agricultural wastes and earthworm fertilizer is done. The food from crops is utilized for the tribal students. Rainwater harvesting project has been carried out by the organization.

4. Girna –tapi janvikas paravaren sanstha (Pachora):

Rainwater harvesting, Tree plantation and its conservation, Environment day celebration, Lecture programmed Slide shows in schools and colleges are some of the main activities carried by the organization.

5. Jivraksha charitable trust: Chalisgaon

The organization works on animal protection and its conservation; mainly on snake conservation, provides medical help to snake bite peoples. The organization also doing work on bird protection. The organization awarded 'Surpatadnya' and 'Laxmi shrinivas' in 2009 from forest department of Maharashtra state.

6. Nehru yuva mandal (Patonda Tal. Chalisgaon):

Tree plantation and conservation, Sanitation Programme, Global warming programme, eco-friendly festival celebration are some of the programmes conducted by the organization. The organization has been awarded with 'Adarsh Mandal Puraskar 2010' for doing work in cultural, educational and environment in Jalgaon District.

7. Dairy multipurpose association (Coda):

Rainwater harvesting, Tree plantation and its conservation are some of the activities carried out by the organization.

8. Udan pakshi mitra sanstha (Amalner):

The organization works on Bird protection and census, Tree plantation, wildlife conservation. The president of the organization, Mr. Ashwin Patil has got 'Green Teacher award' from Rotary club Amalner. He was also awarded by School of environmental and earth sciences NMU Jalgaon in 24th Pakshi Mitra Sammelan 2010.

10. Garudzep pakshi and nisarg seva prashtan(Amalner):

Bird watching and conservation, Habitat and behavior of the Bird, Satpuda Bachav Andolan, tree protection, slide show presentation and poster presentation at school level are some of the programmes conducted by the organization. Mr. Jitendra Wani, President of the organization has been awarded by 'Vasundhara Mitra Puraskar 2010'.

Problems Faced by the NGOs

Funding from government, It was observed that most of the NGOs except one have suffering economical problem. They have difficulty in mobilizing funds from different sources, non-availability of information and procedures regarding funding. Shri. Ashtavinayak Shaikhanik and Sanskrutik Mandal gets funding from government of about 15-20 lakh per year for implementation of Environment awareness programmes. Co-operation from the community and participants, It is very difficult to convince and motivate the community and participants for the implementation of the programmes. It is very difficult to implement environmental legislations by NGOs towards peoples.

Government schemes by Maharashtra State

1. Non conventional energy sources schemes

This scheme is sponsored by Agriculture Department Z.P. Maharashtra State. This scheme had presently 14 solar schemes which passed to Z. P. on 8 October 2003. This

scheme have objective to conservation of solar energy and to minimize the load of the electricity energy other than solar energy. They are funded by Government as

1. farmer Rs. 1750/- (Solar lamp),
2. grampanchayat Rs. 9600/- (Street lamp)
3. grampanchayat Rs. 90% (CFL fitting)

Such schemes have following output products

1. Solar lamp
2. Solar cooker
3. unit of wind mill to generate the electricity

2. Akshay urja ani urja savardhan

This scheme is sponsored by Mahaurja Vikas Abhikaran Department , Maharashtra Government. This scheme is started in 1985. Ministry of New and renewable solar Energy, New Delhi has funded this scheme for Bio gas, wind mill, Bio diesel, production of biotic energy, solar energy. Bank can give 2-3% interest on loan by any personnel purchasing for solar panel under this scheme.

Such schemes have output to energy conservation and to minimize the load shading. All information about this scheme on www.mahaurja.com

3. Paryvaran santulit gram samruddha yojana

This scheme is sponsored by Gram Vikas Vibhag Maharashtra State started 2010. This scheme had been implemented in grampanchayat with the help of local people's and with state government. Such scheme benefits to conservation and protection of environment which even though the villages can utilise for the energy source for standard of living. Purpose of this scheme is to develop the eco-village. Also, this scheme benefits for soil conservation, water conservation, sewage and solid waste management, sanitation and reducing of soil heat. Eligibility criteria of this scheme 10, 000/- population of grampanchayat Rs. 30, 00, 000 and 7001- 10001 population of grampanchayat Rs. 24,00, 00.

In this scheme the specific out put as Tree plantation and protection, waste water and environment management and use of non-conventional energy resources.

4. Rashtriya Harit Sena

This scheme is sponsored by social forestry Department, Maharashtra State (Starting year 2001- 2002). This scheme have implemented on solid waste management, water storage

and pollution control, tree plantation and protection, to awareness the people about environment. In their area they made in 250 school eco-club. Out of this eco-club totally 1250 students are participated. The school have funded Rs. 2500/- for such activity. This has very great impact on children which is positive altitude towards future of India for sustainable development.

5. Vruksha lagvad ani vairan yojana

This scheme is sponsored by social forestry Department, Maharashtra State. This scheme have objective to utilization of waste land for the production of crop. Such scheme is beneficial to poor people in rural area. Presently this scheme have Rs. 1.40, 000/- from total tree species form social forestry.

6. In school level paryvaran seva yojana

This scheme is sponsored by environmental Department Maharashtra State from 14 January 2011. This scheme have objective towards the awareness of environment in primary and secondary school education. They have limitation for implementing scheme i.e In 12 District total 50 primary and secondary schools should be cover. Because of this scheme there should be awareness of environment conservation and protection and also environment education towards young generation. Presently our environmental law can't obey in rural area. This will help for to obey environment law in future generation. This scheme benefits to water, soil and biodiversity conservation, organic farming, energy conservation, utilization of biogas, waste water and solid waste management. For this work scheme also gives scholarship to every student Rs 150/- per month.

7. Sant Tukaram vangram yojana

This scheme is sponsored by forest department, Maharashtra State. Starting 2006 This scheme started by central plant Act 1988 (Sant Tukaram Maharaj) for forest conservation, participation of local people in forest area, forest protection from peoples, protection from forest fire, grazing from animals in forest area,. At presently out of 15500 villages which are on border of forest they established 11799 committees for forest conservation. This scheme is benefits to increase the forest area, minimize the soil erosion to control the food chain, minimize the global warming and pollution control. Under this scheme they sponsored the prizes District level First Prize Rs. 25, 000/-, Second Prize Rs. 15, 000/-, Third Prize Rs. 7,500/-.In state level First Prize Rs. 10,00, 000/-, Second Prize Rs. 5, 00, 000/-

CONCLUSION

1. On the whole, it was found that there were different categories of NGOs such as NGOs with stability fund and stable as well as regular programmes and those who did not have; NGOs who mainly depended on government sponsored programmes and those who had upward linkage with other agencies (national /international)
2. In Jalgaon city 3 out of 5 and in Taluka's of Jalgaon District 4 out of 9 is a small institution with good credibility and is doing considerable work in biodiversity conservation as well as environment education.
3. In Jalgaon city, one NGO (Shri. Ashtavinayak Shaikhanik and Sanskrutik Mandal, NGO) funded by Government and have Jal Swarajya and water irrigation project. This organisation is doing good work in creating environmental awareness among the public. Also another NGO, Orchid nature foundation working area on bird life, has been awarded as "shruthi" for environmental conservation. This organisation is doing good activity especially student community on key environmental issues, and also in the conservation of bio-diversity.
4. Taluka's in Jalgaon District out of nine NGO's, 4 NGOs has been awarded for their work. These are

NGO	Award
Jivraksha charitable trust: Chalisgaon	'Surpatadnya', 'Laxmi shrinivas' in 2009 from forest Department of Maharashtra state
Nehru yuva mandal (Patonda Tal. Chalisgaon)	'Adarsh Mandal Puraskar 2010' for doing work in cultural, educational and environment in Jalgaon District
Udan pakshi mitra sanstha (Amalner)	'Green Teacher award' from Rotary club Amalner to Mr. Ashwin Patil and also from North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon in Pakshi Mitra Samelen
Garudzep pakshi and nisarg seva prashtan(Amalner)	by 'Vasundhara Mitra Puraskar 2010'.

All NGO's are not funded, not supported by Government. But they have different field of work producing their own fund. In general they are doing good work in their field as environment point of view.

5. We had been survey about Government schemes by Maharashtra State which is available in North Maharashtra region. This is our other main flash of our dissertation to awareness of schemes in Jalgaon District. In general all schemes have good opportunity towards the grampanchayat, students and schools for the environment, especially Paryvaran santulit gram samruddha yojana for grampanchayat, Rashtriya Harit Sena for school, in school level paryvaran seva yojana for students, Sant Tukaram vangram yojana for forest conservation at district level and state level.

Table 1: Comparative account of NGOs in Jalgaon city

Name of the Organization	shri.Asthinvinayk shinknik and Sanskrutik Mandal	School of environment	Khandesh nature conservation society	Orchid nature foundation	Vanyajeev Saurakshan Bhahu-uddeshiya sanstha
Address	Ganesh colony	Shau nagar	Mahabal pariser	Mahabal parisar	Shiv colony
Registrion No.	maha.5766/Jalgaon-30/8/2000 f-5522/Jalgaon-20/4/2002	maha-7103/Jalgaon f-6200/Jalgaon		Reg.no-f-11321-2002	maha-10699 Jalgaon
Year of Establishment	2000	2000	2007	2002	2010
Fund Y/N-/	Y	Y	Y	N	N
Trustee	N	N	Y	N	N
Area of Work	Awareness	Programme	Wild life	Bird life	Snake
Projects undertaken	Y	N	N	N	N
Government collaboration with NGO	Y	N	N	N	N

Table 2: Comparative account of NGOs in Taluka's in Jalgaon District.

Name of the Organization	Upaj (Urja Paryavaran Jal)	Green Earth foundation	Go vityan anusandhan Bhahu-uddeshiya santha	Girna -tapi janvikas paravaren sanstha	Jivraksha charitable trust	Nehru yuva mandal	Dhairya multipurpose association	Udan pakshi mitra sanstha	Garudzep pakshi and nisarg seva prashtan
Address	Bhusawal	Bhusawal	Yawal	Pachora	Chalisingaon	Patonda Tal. Chalisingaon	Chopda	Amlner	Amlner
Registration No.	maha-7180/Jalgaon	maha-11015/Jalgaon	Maha-6955 Jalgaon-14-	maha-10341/Jalgaon-	maha-1062	maha-6256 Jalgaon-	Maha-10336	maha-11364-	maha-8399-

		30-8-09	1-03	2008	Jalgaon-2000	2004		Jalgaon	Jalgaon
Year of Establishment	2003	2009	2003	2008	2000	2004	2003	2005	2006
Fund Y/N/-	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
Trustee	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
Area of Work	Non conventional energy resources	Programme	Bio gas	Population	Awareness	Snake	programme	Social envi.	School envi.
Projects undertaken	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
Government collaboration with NGO	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
Awareness Media	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Programme conduct – In school/colleges/city/village.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Training Activity	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Public participation	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Awards	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	Y	N

Table 3: Comparative account of Government Scheme in Taluka's of Jalgaon District.

Sr. No.	Schemes Name	Sponsored by	Year of Start
1.	Non conventional energy sources schemes	Krushi vibhag, z.p	2000
2.	Akshay urja ani urja savardhan	Mahaurja vikas abhikaran	1985
3.	Paryvaran santulit gram samruddha yojana	Gram vikas vibhag	2010
4.	Rashtriya Harit Sena	Social forestry	2001-2002
5.	Vruksha lagvad ani vairan yojana	Social forestry	-----
6.	In school level paryvaran seva yojana	Environment sci. department	2011
7.	Sant Tukaram vangram yojana	Forest department	2006

6. References

1. How To Build A Good Small NGO Section E: Building On Good Principles and Practice, www.networklearning.org/
2. C. Villi, Report on A Study on "The Role of NGOs in Social Mobilizations in the Context of SGSY" National Institute of Rural Development, Hyderabad 2006.
3. M. V. Bharambe 2009, Report on "Nisarg va Paryavaran Premi vyakti va sansthanchi suchi", Bhusawal Dist. Jalgaon.
4. Environmental communication and the cultural politics of environmental citizenship Burgess J, Harrison C M, Filius P, 1998 *Environment and Planning A* 30(8) 1445 – 1460
5. Chitra, A. "Role of Ngo's in Protecting Environment And Health" Proceedings of the Third International Conference on Environment and Health, Chennai, India, 15-17 December, 2003. Chennai: Department of Geography, University of Madras and Faculty of Environmental Studies, York University. Pages 105 – 112.

